

FORMATION OF REQUIREMENTS FOR SPECIAL CLOTHING FOR WORKERS IN THE OIL AND GAS EXTRACTION INDUSTRY

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Abstract. *The article provides a scientific analysis of the main requirements for protective clothing used by workers in the oil and gas extraction industry. The study examines the types and regulatory standards of work-wear for specialists employed in this field, such as operators, drillers, repair technicians, welders, fitters, and electricians.*

Keywords: *special clothing, oil and gas extraction, labor protection, protection requirements, ergonomics, special clothing, requirements, well drilling, coating.*

Introduction

The hazardous and complex working conditions in the oil and gas extraction industry make it crucial to reliably protect workers, ensuring their labor protection and industrial safety [1]. In oil and gas extraction, operations are carried out by oil and gas production operators and workers of the well capital repair brigade.

Image 1. *Types of worker professions employed in a well repair brigade in oil and gas extraction.*

Image 1 shows the types of worker professions employed in a well repair brigade in oil and gas extraction, such as drilling operator, repair operator, driller for capital repair, driller's assistant, and lift machine operator. Operators play a key role in oil and gas extraction operations. They manage the technological process at the well using all available methods and ensure uninterrupted work. Each well is monitored daily by an operator; all equipment and the area are visually inspected; technological parameters of operating wells are recorded; product samples are taken for operational analysis; and repair work is carried out when necessary [2].

Oil and gas extraction is not seasonal work but is carried out year-round. Each shift lasts 12 hours. Considering that the main types of work in oil field operation are carried out outdoors, and that extracted oil, its components, various chemical reagents, toxic and explosive substances

often damage special clothing, the importance of their protective properties is determined [3]. The procedure for providing workers in the oil and gas extraction sector with special clothing (SC) according to their professions is presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Norm for Providing Special Clothing to Workers in the Oil and Gas Extraction Industry

Garment Types and Worker Specialists	Provision Norm (Industry Standard)
Operator Summer cotton-padded jacket and trousers Winter insulated jacket and trousers	1 set per year 1 set every 2 years
Driller and Driller's Assistant, Repairer, Welder, Fitter, Electrician Summer cotton suit Footwear (Boots) Headgear (Helmet) Gloves Winter insulated jacket and trousers	1 set per year 1 pair every 3 years 1 item every 3 years 1 pair per year 1 set every 2 years
Lab Assistant-Collector Summer cotton-padded jacket and trousers Winter insulated jacket and trousers	1 set per year 1 set every 2 years
Installer Summer cotton suit and trousers Winter insulated jacket and trousers	1 set per year 1 set every 2 years

According to the standard, operators, drillers and their assistants, repairers, welders, fitters, electricians, lab assistant-collectors, and derrick installers are provided with one set of summer SC per year, one set of winter SC every two years, and one headgear (helmet) every three years.

Analysis of the types and characteristics of the aforementioned professions shows that the main share of this sector of the economy is related to oil and gas extraction [4]. Oil and gas extraction is characterized by arduous types of work carried out year-round, day and night, in desert areas under any climatic conditions.

A set of main requirements for special clothing for workers in the oil and gas extraction industry is presented, which includes protective, ergonomic, structural-technological, and aesthetic indicators that allow for the selection of the SC design and suitable fabrics for its manufacture [5]. Based on these requirements, recommendations have been developed to improve the comfort, durability, and level of protection of workers' clothing.

Special clothing must protect the human body from the following harmful production effects:

- ♣ general industrial soiling and mechanical impacts;
- ♣ high (low) temperatures and wind, storms, sandstorms;
- ♣ contamination by oil and oil products;
- ♣ accumulation of static electricity on the surface of special clothing;

- ♣ contact with heated surfaces and tools;
- ♣ chemical reagents used for oil and gas extraction;
- ♣ explosive gas mixtures;
- ♣ harmful biological factors (bites of desert insects);
- ♣ sparks of molten metals;
- ♣ open flame and electric shock;
- ♣ water and rainfall;

Requirements for the fabric:

-Main fabric - 100% cotton, cotton-polyester, anti-static thread, cotton content should not be less than 65%;

-Protective coating - must have an oil-water-petroleum repellent coating;

-Minimum fabric density - 230 g/m²;

-Fabric tensile strength (warp / weft) - 1100/700 N;

-Fabric shrinkage after 5 washes: warp no more than 4%;

-Weft no more than 2%;

-Abrasion resistance - not less than 7000 cycles;

-Air permeability - not less than 30 cm³/cm²*s;

-Hygroscopicity - should be between 5-14%;

-Oil repellency - not less than 4 points;

In accordance with GOST 11209-2014, BS EN 1149-3:2004, BS EN 533:1997 standards

[6].

Requirements for the SC design:

- Must correspond to the dimensions of the human body and ensure the dynamics of body parts;
- Must ensure the structure of the human body and the statics of body parts (comfort of clothing in relation to human body structure);
- Special clothing must ensure the human posture;
- The main fabric colors for corporate special clothing should be black, blue, and gray;
- Special clothing must retain its protective properties throughout the specified service life, i.e., 12 months.

Ergonomic requirements:

- Functional placement and optimal parameters of special clothing parts and components, and ease of use of its individual elements;
- Possibility to ensure heat exchange with the external environment through ventilation openings in areas with the highest perspiration during changes in physical activity levels;
- Possibility to adjust the special clothing (parts or components) in width, length, and volume through functional elements for a better fit to the worker's physique and to prevent local clinging to the body.

Requirements for clothing technology:

- ❖ Seam breaking strength should not be less than 250 N;
- ❖ Reinforcing pads should be present on the elbow areas and the cuff of the jacket, and on the knee area of the trousers. The knee protection area should not be less than 270 mm, and the protective pad must be placed at least 100 mm above the knee line;
- ❖ Protective mesh should be present in the areas intended for ventilation holes;

- ❖ Holes for ventilation located along the bottom edge of the jacket should have a free seam allowance of at least 10 mm for air exchange and not less than 70 mm in the finished state;
- ❖ The width of reflective tapes is recommended to be 50 mm;
- ❖ The color of threads used for special clothing seams should match [7].

Since the work activities of workers in the oil and gas extraction industry take place in difficult and hazardous conditions, the requirements for their special clothing are very important. According to research results, special clothing must not only protect against mechanical and chemical impacts but also maintain the worker's physiological state stable in various climatic conditions.

The physico-mechanical properties of fabrics, air permeability and hygroscopicity indicators, as well as ergonomic solutions in the clothing design ensure comfort for the worker. Based on this, the developed special clothing not only increases worker safety but also improves labor productivity.

Conclusion

Studying the properties of materials intended for performing the protective function of special clothing, recommending the most suitable ones, and preparing technical documentation for an industrial sample that meets the requirements is important.

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